

THE ROLE OF SPEECH ACTIVITY IN THE DEVELOPMENT AND EVOLUTION OF LANGUAGE

Malikova Iroda

Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Abstract. *Modern linguistics studies language as a complex system, which necessitates the analysis of paradigmatic and syntagmatic relationships. These relationships allow individual language units to interact with others across various levels of linguistic structure. Each language unit is connected and realized through paradigmatic and syntagmatic relationships, making them essential components for the functioning of the language system. All linguistic units participate in paradigms, while syntagmatic interactions transform these units into speech elements during speech activity.*

Introduction

In his book "F. de Saussure's Linguistic Conception", I. Quchqortoyev writes: "The primary concern for a language user is the current state of the language (its synchronic state), as this is defined by the existing system of linguistic tools. From this perspective, only the synchronic state of language constitutes a system. However, this view, while significant for linguistics, cannot fully explain the nature of language. Language is an adaptive tool that evolves in response to communicative needs, and this adaptation occurs continuously during the speech process." [1:31-32]. According to Saussure, speech activity has two aspects: individual and social, which are inseparable. In addressing the question, "What is language?", he emphasizes that the concept of "language" is not equivalent to "speech activity." Instead, language is a component—though the most significant one—of speech activity. It is a social product and exists in the memory of individual speakers, allowing them to engage in speech activity. This connection between individual memory and speech activity aligns with cognitive linguistics, which is grounded in the theory of knowledge and emphasizes the human factor. Information about reality finds expression in human cognition and consciousness. Similarly, pragmatolinguistics, with its focus on human-centric factors, directly intersects with cognitive linguistics. Sh. Safarov notes: "When discussing cognitive activity, it is important to consider not only reasoning and intellectual processes but also the outcomes of thought and associated non-mental phenomena." [3:10]. A. Kuchiboyev elaborates on the role of cognitive knowledge in speech activity, stating: "Cognitive knowledge facilitates the perception of implicit meaning through presuppositions and contextual interpretation, leading to the comprehension of speech." [4:15]. These views highlight the crucial role of the human factor in addressing linguistic problems from cognitive and pragmatic perspectives. E.A. Popova affirms this, stating: "It is difficult to imagine the progress of linguistics without considering the human factor. In earlier periods, linguistics was entirely devoid of human considerations." [5:69]

Popova seems to blur the lines between internal and external linguistic issues. While the human factor undeniably plays a critical role in language evolution, it is considered an external linguistic element. Despite the direct connection between language systems and human cognition, language operates within its internal rules. This distinction validates Saussure's division of linguistics into internal and external domains.

However, recognizing the autonomy of internal linguistics does not diminish the importance of external linguistic factors. Saussure himself acknowledges: "Studying external linguistic factors—non-linguistic phenomena—is essential. However, the internal structure of language can still be studied independently of these factors, as language is a system governed by its internal order." [2:31]. This insight suggests that while external factors contribute to

language application, internal linguistics is centered on the structural principles unique to the language system.

R. Saifullayeva and colleagues classify paradigms into larger and smaller systems, as well as external and internal paradigms. For example, consonants can be categorized as voiced and voiceless, representing smaller paradigms. The broader consonant system, in turn, constitutes a larger paradigm.

These paradigms highlight associative relationships within linguistic systems, often referred to as systemic or paradigmatic relations. Saussure also differentiates between the linguistics of language (*langue*) and speech (*parole*), advocating for the study of both while emphasizing their distinction. He writes: "For three thousand years, linguistics has focused on language. Now, it is time to study speech, which remains an underexplored field awaiting researchers." [2:29].

The very existence of the language system is tied to speech activity, as its nature and essence are revealed through communicative processes. Consequently, the semantic properties of linguistic units are realized and clarified in speech. In his work "Semantics", Sh. Safarov highlights the critical role of nomination (naming) in speech activity, stating: "The process of linguistic sign selection during naming—whether arbitrary or motivated—is a fundamental issue in theoretical linguistics." [8:20]. The interconnected nature of linguistic elements ensures that their paradigmatic and syntagmatic relationships become apparent during speech. Though differing in linguistic status, these relationships are interdependent and can be observed in the interaction of units across language levels.

A. Nurmonov, reflecting on speech activity, references V. Humboldt's idea that language is not a static *ergon* (product) but rather a dynamic *energeia* (energy). Based on this premise, he concludes that the primary object of linguistic study should be speech activity. He argues: "Speech activity integrates the social and individual dimensions of language, forming a complex process rooted in the dialectical relationship between language (*langue*) and speech (*parole*)." [9:17].

Paradigmatic relationships are defined by several key features:

1. When one member of a paradigm is recalled, other members of the same paradigm are also brought to mind.
2. In any specific speech situation, only one member of a paradigm is chosen.
3. Paradigm members share similarities while differing in at least one distinctive feature.
4. Members can replace or substitute one another in specific contexts.

These characteristics underline the essential role paradigmatic relationships play in shaping language as a system and enabling its use in speech.

Studying language as an integrated system aids in understanding speech activity. Modern linguistics distinguishes between language and speech, resulting in the scientific development of both linguistic domains. While language linguistics has been extensively studied over three millennia, speech linguistics remains an emerging field requiring further exploration. Sh. Safarov notes: "The system-structural paradigm resolved many of the shortcomings of earlier approaches, which often analyzed linguistic phenomena in isolation. However, this paradigm introduced its own limitations, such as the separation of language from its user—humans. Efforts to address these shortcomings led to the development of pragmatic and cognitive linguistic paradigms." [7:38].

The hierarchical organization of linguistic elements involves selecting units from various levels—phonemes, morphemes, words, phrases, and sentences—each contributing to the construction of meaning. For example, phonemes combine to form sounds and letters, while morphemes contribute to lexemes, and words build sentences and texts.

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